

Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth system

IEnKS algorithm for initialising coupled ice - ocean models

Milestone MS8

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Means of verification of the achievement of the milestone

Model validated. Partner in charge of delivery of the milestone: UKRI-BAS.

- Test cases are presented below.
- Code is available at <https://github.com/RJArthern/KalmanEnsembling.git> WAVI_ENKF
- An EGU abstract has been submitted that uses the algorithm [1].

Work performed and main achievements

Application of the Iterative Ensemble Kalman Filter to the WAVI ice sheet model.

Background

Model State: Coupled Ice/Ocean models evolve a collection of variables to represent the changes of the ice sheet and the surrounding ocean. Together, these variables (ice thickness, ocean velocity, pressure, temperature, salinity, etc.) represent the model state.

KF: The Kalman Filter (KF) provides an efficient means for updating a model state so that it agrees with observations. The algorithm also provides a corresponding update to the error covariance. After a succession of sequential observations, good estimates of the state variables and their errors can be obtained.

EnKF: Retaining the full error covariance matrix in the calculations can be expensive. This has led to the development of the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) [2]. Here a collection of model runs (i.e., an ensemble) is performed and the sample covariance of this ensemble is used in place of the full covariance matrix.

IEnKF/IEnKS: Non-linear models require an additional iteration loop, as in the Iterative Ensemble Kalman Filter (IEnKF). If all the observational data are included at once, rather than sequentially, the method is referred to as an Iterative Ensemble Kalman Smoother (IEnKS) [3].

Model Parameters: As well as state variables, coupled Ice/Ocean models also contain physical parameters (coefficients of viscosity, drag, mixing etc.). If these are not specified accurately, the model will provide inaccurate ocean and ice conditions and inaccurate projections of sea level.

EKI: When Ensemble Kalman methods like IEnKF/IEnKS are used, but the focus is on estimating the best values for parameters, rather than state variables, we refer to Ensemble Kalman Inversion (EKI).

Implementation

To deploy the methods described above, we have combined:

- 1) **EnsembleKalmanProcesses.jl:** A Julia package to implement the IEnKF [4].
- 2) **model-ensampler:** A tool for managing processes on a SLURM cluster [5].

3) WAVI.jl: An ice sheet model written in Julia [6].

Figure 1. Workflow for obtaining improved parameter estimates using an Ensemble Kalman Filter. We use *EnsembleKalmanProcesses.jl* to Initialise the ensemble and perform updates using data. The separate ensemble members of the WAVI ice sheet model are run in parallel on a SLURM cluster, managed by the model-ensampler tool.

A simple test case

As a proof of concept, we have implemented a simple test case that estimates the initial thickness of an ice sheet from synthetic observations of its thickness at a later time. The figure shows the reduction in root-mean-square error on the initial thickness estimates after a successive number of iterations. This shows the ability of the approach to reduce errors in the initial values for state variables.

Figure 2. Reduction in the error on initial thickness estimates after successive iterations

The code to implement this simple example is available at the following GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/RJArthern/KalmanEnsembling.git> Branch: WAVI_ENKF

Multiple parameter estimation

(In collaboration with the PROTECT project)

The simple example shown above has already been extended to a more complicated situation estimating multiple parameters (Bradley et al., in preparation, [1]). Here a 300-year simulation using the WAVI ice sheet model on an idealised domain was constrained to agree with synthetic observations of ice volume. The figure shows the trajectory of the ice volume over time after successive iterations. As the iterations proceed, the agreement with the observations improves, and improved estimates of the model parameters are obtained.

Figure 3. Simultaneous estimation of multiple parameters for the WAVI ice model. Successive iterations reduce the mismatch between the model and synthetic observations of ice volume, shown in black with error bars [1].

Conclusion

Early results of using the Iterative Ensemble Kalman Filter/Smoothener to initialise coupled Ice/Ocean models for historical hindcast simulations are promising. A workflow to deploy these methods on a HPC cluster has been developed and some test cases have been completed. The approach could easily be adapted for use with other models in the OCEAN:ICE project.

References

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